

REACTIONS WITH DRY ALKALINE EARTH HYDROXIDES. PART IV, A NEW METHOD FOR THE PREPARATION OF ANILINE

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Nitrobenzene has been reduced to aniline to the extent 54.0% by leading its vapour over a mixture of sulphur and calcium hydroxide containing 20% of sulphur and heated to a temperature of about 200°.

Several procedures have been suggested for the reduction of liquid nitrobenzene. In the vapour phase, however, the work seems to have been tried only through the agency of gaseous hydrogen, activated by the presence of catalysts (Gladstone and Tribe, *Chem. News*, 1878, 37, 68; Yosikawa and Yamanuka, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Japan*, 1925, 14, 406; Paul and Roth, *Ber.*, 1938, 41, 2282). According to Griffith and Brown (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 477) the yield of aniline can be raised as high as 97% using CoS as the catalyst and a temperature of about 300°. From the work of Sabatier and Sanderenes (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, 135, 226), however, it appears that the yield of aniline in such processes comes best in the neighbourhood of 200°, an elevation to 300° favouring the formation of ammonia etc.

It has been observed in the earlier studies (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 751) that heated mixtures of lime and carbon or lime and sulphur can reduce a nitrate to ammonia. The fate of organic nitro compounds under similar treatment naturally constitutes a matter of interesting study. The object in the present piece of work was to utilise the above mentioned mixtures for the vapour phase reduction of a volatile nitro compound, nitrobenzene being primarily chosen because of the industrial importance associated with aniline, its final reduction product.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitrobenzene used in this work was one of 'Analar' quality. Other reagents were the same as used in earlier works (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 101, 394).

Qualitative tests were conducted by taking 2 c.c. of nitrobenzene in test tubes in each of the experiments and covering the same with respective lime-sulphur mixture in the proportions as shown in Table I. The charge was compressed, provided with a central hole (1 mm.), closed with a delivery tube dipping under dilute HCl, and arranged horizontally as in other experiments described earlier (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 394, 751). Heat was first applied to the upper region of the charge with the help of a small flame till a bubble or two of H₂S began to appear. It was then transferred lower to vaporise the nitrobenzene. The starting of the reaction was noticed by the evolution of a rapid stream of H₂S gas and the appearance of a distillation product, either solid or liquid or both in the long delivery tube.

The supply of heat at this stage was controlled by lowering the flame and playing it rapidly, so that the distillation continued at a regular though slow pace, but the evolution of H_2S was reduced to a minimum. It was noticed that with the increase in the supply of heat, volume of the gas evolution and the amount of unchanged nitrobenzene distilled increased. On the other hand, with controlled heating, the distilled liquid dissolved completely in the acid and the gas evolution was totally stopped. As a precautionary measure the individual experiments were carried out for not less than 2 hours. At the close of the experiments, the solid product deposited inside the delivery tube was washed down with alcohol and filtered free of sulphur. The alcoholic solution, on evaporation left varying amounts of a residue which in some cases was in traces or absent. The amount of nitrobenzene distilled out also varied from appreciable to traces or nil. Aniline was detected by basifying the (filtered and boiled) acidic collection in the receiver with an excess of concentrated NaOH solution. In case of amine in trace, it had to be detected by the usual confirmatory tests. Ammonia was found by the intensity of its tests to occur in varying extents in different experiments. Results of the above set of experiments conducted with mixtures of diminishing sulphur concentrations are shown in Table I, where as usual 'p' indicates presence, 'tr', trace formations and 'n', absence of the products referred against. The residue of the reaction was found to contain sulphide, sulphite and sulphate of calcium

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Lime.	Sulphur.	S : Ca(OH) ₂ .	Products			
				Solid.	PhNO ₂ .	Ph NH ₂ .	NH
a	22 g.	11 g.	1 : 2	p	p	tr	tr
b	24	8	1 : 3	p	p	tr	tr
c	24	6	1 : 4	tr	tr	p	p
d	25	5	1 : 5	n	n	p	p
e	30	5	1 : 6	n	n	p	p

Identical experiments with calcium hydroxide-carbon mixtures revealed that nitrobenzene distilled out entirely unchanged irrespective of the concentration of carbon.

Quantitative estimation of the aniline, formed by the reduction of nitrobenzene by the above process, was conducted in the same way as described above. The receivers in these cases contained pure water. At the end of the experiment, the heavy liquid, found settled at the bottom of the aqueous layer, was measured out by means of a graduated pipette, treated with a warm solution of HCl (conc., 3 c. c., 15%), and the undissolved nitrobenzene remeasured. From the readings obtained the volumes of the reacted nitrobenzene and the corresponding

aniline formed were found out. Results of the experiments with 5 c. c. of nitrobenzene in each case are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Expt. No.	Ca(OH) ₂ .	Sulphur.	Aniline found.	% Transformation.
a	32 g.	4 g.	2.04 g.	45.0
b	35	5	2.24	49.3
c	36	6	2.34	51.5
d	35	7	2.45	54.0

The optimum temperature at which the reduction of nitrobenzene to aniline took place was determined as in the manner described in Part I (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 101). Nitrobenzene (2 c. c.) was taken in each case and covered with 30 g. of the mixture of lime and sulphur having the same composition as in Table II. The compressed charge, after being fitted with a thermometer at the centre of the mass and a delivery tube, was placed horizontally on a stand. A preliminary heating was given with the help of a small flame to raise the temperature of the mass to about 100°. The flame was then localised mainly below the region containing the bulb of the thermometer, but occasionally removed to the bottom to ensure the distillation of nitrobenzene. As soon as the droplets of aniline, emulsified with water, were seen to appear in the receiver, the flame was lowered at least six inches below the tube, so that only a current of warm air grazed its surface serving as an insulation against the loss of heat. The temperature was seen to rise, attain a maximum, remain steady for a few seconds, and then recede. During all this period the distillation of aniline continued, subsiding, however, with the fall of the temperature. This maximum obviously represents the temperature attained by the charge during the optimum reduction to aniline. It was, however, not found identical in different experiments and even with the same mixture it showed good variations, evidently being caused by the differences in the compression, draft of the wind, timing of the heating, etc. Results of different experiments gave 183° as the mean value. Considering the loss of heat sustained by the charge, it is obvious that the optimum temperature will be somewhat higher, 200° representing the ideal temperature because of the facts that it is far below the temperature at which sulphur and Ca(OH)₂ begin to react effectively (vide this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 101) and that it is practically the highest at which nitrobenzene does not begin to distil freely.

DISCUSSION

Results of the qualitative tests given above indicate that nitrobenzene being led over a heated mixture of lime and carbon is not affected in any way, whereas the same treatment with lime-sulphur mixture transforms it into various reduction

products. The stage of reduction depends on the concentration of sulphur in the mixture. When the same is high, more than 33%, the reduction proceeds mainly to the partial stage (Table I, expts. a & b), the nature of which remains to be studied in a later communication. With lowering in the sulphur ratio the formation of aniline gains greater prominence, and with 20% of sulphur in the mixture, this seems to be the only product of the reduction, accompanied, however, with some ammonia. The latter appears to be produced in increasing quantities with the rise in the lime concentration, and is obviously a product from the decomposition of aniline, caused by the heated mass of the base, as, in general, is known to produce such effects (Schulze, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1867, 6, 374).

Quantitative estimations (Table II) show that the yield of aniline increases with the rise in the net quantity of sulphur taken in the reaction mixture, and with an weight of the latter almost equal to that of nitrobenzene treated, the same is about 54.0%. Possibly a larger yield can be obtained using a higher proportions of sulphur. Necessitating, however, the addition of a corresponding increased quantity of lime, the mixture was found unwieldy to be treated in such small-scale experiments. Experiments in connection with the determination of the reaction temperature clearly indicate the reaction to be exothermic; and in any case of large scale working, a system of cooling will have to be introduced to keep the temperature down to about 200°, the highest limit wherein reduction of nitrobenzene by lime-sulphur mixture seems to be carried out with best of advantages.

It has been noticed that, when the evolution of H_2S is brisk, as with a high concentration of sulphur in the mixture or with the elevation of the reaction temperature, the formation of aniline is hampered. This, however, is found to be favoured with rather an increased concentration of lime, wherein the chance of the free existence of H_2S is lower. It is thus evident that the reduction of nitrobenzene, in the process under discussion, can hardly be due to the action of H_2S . It is indeed difficult to explain this reduction as also of sulphur found to occur simultaneously except as the work of nascent hydrogen. The precise manner of this mechanism remains to be discussed in a later communication together with the consideration of the cause of the general reducing property possessed by mixtures of dry alkaline earth hydroxides with several non-metallic elements.